

Effects of reducing sedentary behavior on liver insulin sensitivity, liver fat content, and liver enzyme levels: A six-month randomized controlled trial

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Supplementary material

Supplementary figures

Supplementary figure 1. The individual change in measured sedentary behavior (SB) time (hours/day) of each participant (n=39) with valid accelerometer data during the intervention. Intervention group (blue bar) and control group (red bar).

Supplementary figure 2. MRS-measured liver fat content (%) at baseline for each participant (n=40).

Supplementary figure 3. Insulin sensitivity marker results of the intervention (black line) and control (grey line) groups at baseline and after six months of A) fasting glucose, B) fasting insulin, and C) HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin. The values are presented as model-based means (95 % CI), ^a = log10 transformed (means are back-transformed geometric model-based means [95% CI]).

Supplementary figure 4. Lipid marker results of the intervention (black line) and control (grey line) groups at baseline and after six months of A) fasting triglycerides; B) NEFA, non-esterified fatty acids; C) cholesterol; D) HDL-C, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and E) LDL-C, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol. The values are presented as model-based means (95 % CI), ^a = log₁₀ transformed (means are back-transformed geometric model-based means [95% CI]).

